

SFigure 1.

Deep and Lobar ICH Subjects Do Not Separate By Time Since Event

SFigure 2.

Per-Gene List Generation

SFigure 3.

Top 100 DeepPerGene Genes Differentiate Deep ICH from VRFC

SFigure 4.

Top 100 LobarPerGene Genes Differentiate Deep ICH from VRFC

SFigure 5. T Cell Receptor Signaling Pathway with LobarPerGene Expression Predicts Activation of Inflammatory Outputs

SFigure 6.

DeepVsLobar Gene List Differentiates Deep and Lobar ICH from VRFC

SFigure 8.

DeepICHandVRFC Network Dendrogram

SFigure 9.

BEX2 Signaling in DC-Grey60 Implicates Increased Cell Death of Dopaminergic Neurons

SFigure 10.

LobarICHandVRFC Network Dendrogram

SFigure 11.

Amyloid Processing is Predicted Activated in LC-Pink

SFigure 12.

Venn Diagram of Deep and Lobar ICH Significant Canonical Pathways

Deep Significant Pathways

BH $p < 0.05$

Lobar Significant Pathways

BH $p < 0.05$

